

A mathematical framework for polarization algebra of deterministic optical systems

M. A. Kuntman and E. Kuntman

June 26, 2019

Abstract

In general, Jones formalism of polarization optics refers to deterministic optical systems represented by 2×2 complex Jones matrices acting on totally polarized light states represented by two dimensional complex Jones vectors. On the other hand, Stokes-Mueller formalism deals only with real states, hence it cannot account for phases introduced by optical systems. But, Stokes-Mueller formalism has an advantage over the Jones formalism that it works with directly measurable parameters, therefore it is desirable to merge these two approaches into a single formalism that links the real-measurable states with complex states. In previous works it was shown that there exists a 4×4 complex matrix that can keep track of the phase introduced by the deterministic optical system. This complex matrix transforms real Stokes vectors into four dimensional complex vectors related with phase. Recently a theorem was introduced. The theorem states that, for deterministic optical systems, there exists a relation between the outer products of real-measurable input-output Stokes vectors and four dimensional complex state vectors of totally polarized light. In this note these results are combined in a compact mathematical framework.

1 Introduction

A mathematical framework for deterministic optical systems is considered. The state of the light is always assumed to be totally polarized. Extensions to depolarization and partial polarization will be studied elsewhere. Only four dimensional vector and matrix states are discussed, correspondence with quaternion states and Jones formalism is not included.

A proposed complex valued four parameter formulation [1]- [4] is an extension of the real valued Stokes-Mueller formulation of deterministic optical systems. Theoretical framework is based on four dimensional complex $|h\rangle$ vectors and 4×4 complex \mathbf{Z} matrices that are devised to keep track of phases introduced by deterministic optical systems.

Basic elements of the formalism are depicted in Figure (1). Mathematical framework consists of three parts: First part (upper block in Fig.(1)) comprises various forms of complex valued states of deterministic optical systems. Second part (lower block in Fig.(1)) is about real and complex valued states of totally polarized light. Real states of the theory that can be

Figure 1: A mathematical framework for polarization optics.

obtained by intensity measurements reside in the third part of the mathematical framework (right block in Fig.(1)).

States of the optical system, $|h\rangle$ and \mathbf{Z} are basic elements of the theory which are closely related with each other. $|h\rangle$ is a vector state and \mathbf{Z} is a matrix state. $\mathfrak{H} = |h\rangle\langle h|$ is a complex-Hermitian matrix constructed by an outer product of $|h\rangle$ with its Hermitian conjugate. \mathbf{M} is a real matrix which can be named as Mueller-Jones matrix of the deterministic optical system. If \mathbf{Z} matrices are considered elementary states then it is possible to regard $\mathbf{M} = \mathbf{Z}\mathbf{Z}^*$ as a definition of the Mueller-Jones matrix. It is also possible to obtain \mathbf{M} by a Σ transformation, $\mathbf{M} = \Sigma(\mathfrak{H})$. Therefore, there are two routs that the complex states of the system meet real states. The Mueller-Jones matrix is the interface between two parts of the mathematical framework.

Real and complex states corresponding to totally polarized light reside in the lower block of Figure (1). $|s\rangle$ and \mathbf{S} are different forms of the real Stokes vector which are closely related with each other. $|s\rangle$ is a real vector state and \mathbf{S} is a complex matrix state. \mathbf{Z} matrix transforms the real Stokes vector, $|s\rangle$, into a complex vector $|\tilde{s}\rangle$: $\mathbf{Z}|s\rangle = |\tilde{s}\rangle$. \mathbf{Z} matrix also transforms the complex Stokes matrix, \mathbf{S} , into another complex matrix, $\tilde{\mathbf{S}}$: $\mathbf{Z}\mathbf{S} = \tilde{\mathbf{S}}$. $\mathfrak{G} = |\tilde{s}\rangle\langle\tilde{s}|$ is a complex-Hermitian matrix constructed by an outer product of $|\tilde{s}\rangle$ with its Hermitian conjugate. On the other hand, $\mathbf{K} = \tilde{\mathbf{S}}\tilde{\mathbf{S}}^*$ is a matrix which is real and equal to the outer product of real input and output Stokes vectors, $\mathbf{K} = |s'\rangle\langle s|$. If \mathbf{S} and $\tilde{\mathbf{S}}$ matrices are considered as the elementary states of the totally polarized light then it is possible to regard $\mathbf{K} = \tilde{\mathbf{S}}\tilde{\mathbf{S}}^*$ as a definition of \mathbf{K} matrix. It is also possible to obtain \mathbf{K} by a Σ transformation as $\mathbf{K} = \Sigma(\mathfrak{G})$ [5]. Again, there are two routs that complex polarization states of light meet real states of light, where \mathbf{K} matrix is the interface between two parts of the mathematical

framework.

This framework is designed to follow the arrows in Fig.(1). For example, start with a given complex \mathbf{Z} matrix and define the corresponding real (measurable) matrix, \mathbf{M} , as $\mathbf{M} = \mathbf{Z}\mathbf{Z}^*$, or start with a vector state $|h\rangle$ and follow the upper route to find \mathbf{M} by a Σ transformation. Since there are two possible ways of calculating \mathbf{M} , it is possible to put forward a theorem that manifests the internal structure of the theory: $\mathbf{Z}\mathbf{Z}^* = \Sigma(\mathfrak{H})$.

It is also possible to proceed in the reverse direction. For example, start with a given real Mueller-Jones matrix, \mathbf{M} , and try to find the \mathbf{Z} matrix. But, when one proceeds in the reverse direction there is no one-to-one correspondence with real matrices and complex matrices because of the phase phase issue [6]. An application of this method was given in [7], where, \mathfrak{H} is obtained first from \mathbf{M} , and by using the property that $rank(\mathfrak{H}) = 1$, it was shown that the vector state $|h\rangle$ can be obtained apart from an overall phase.

It is also possible to do similar things for polarization states of totally polarized light. For example, start with a given real-measured \mathbf{K} matrix and try to find the \mathbf{S} matrix. Or, follow the second route first to obtain \mathfrak{S} from \mathbf{K} by a Σ transformation, then, by using the property that $rank(\mathfrak{S}) = 1$ try to show that the vector state $|\tilde{s}\rangle$ can be obtained apart from an overall phase. An application of this method was given and it was shown that it could be possible to calculate \mathbf{Z} matrix via \mathbf{K} matrix by using the results of only two polarimetric measurements [8].

2 Definitions of states

In this section details of the formalism is worked out. There are two types of mathematical objects:

- Expressions that correspond to deterministic optical systems.
- Expressions that correspond to totally polarized light.

2.1 States representing deterministic optical systems

Only four dimensional vector states and 4×4 matrix states of deterministic optical systems are considered. 2×2 Jones matrices could be rendered as equivalent forms.

(i) A vector state $|h\rangle$ generates a Mueller-Jones matrix. $|h\rangle$ is described by four dimensionless parameters τ , α , β and γ :

$$|h\rangle = \begin{pmatrix} \tau \\ \alpha \\ \beta \\ \gamma \end{pmatrix}, \quad (1)$$

where τ , α , β and γ are generally complex numbers that can be related with basic anisotropy parameters of the optical system [2]. If the overall phase is not taken into account, one of the parameters, for example τ , can be chosen to be real and positive. In that case, the number of independent parameters will be seven. It is also possible to take $\tau = 1$ for convenience, and this reduces the number of unknown parameters to six.

(ii) A matrix state \mathbf{Z} is also defined in terms of parameters τ, α, β and γ and it is just another form of generators of Mueller-Jones matrices:

$$\mathbf{Z} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} \tau & \alpha & \beta & \gamma \\ \alpha & \tau & -i\gamma & i\beta \\ \beta & i\gamma & \tau & -i\alpha \\ \gamma & -i\beta & i\alpha & \tau \end{pmatrix}. \quad (2)$$

It has been shown that $|h\rangle$ vectors are closely related with \mathbf{Z} matrices, 2×2 complex Jones matrices and complex valued quaternions [4].

A real Mueller-Jones matrix is defined as a product of \mathbf{Z} matrix with its complex conjugate:

$$\mathbf{M} = \mathbf{Z}\mathbf{Z}^* = \mathbf{Z}^*\mathbf{Z}. \quad (3)$$

Eq.(3) leads to an expression for the Mueller-Jones matrix in terms of parameters τ, α, β and γ :

$$\mathbf{M} = \frac{1}{2} \begin{pmatrix} \frac{\tau\tau^* + \alpha\alpha^*}{\beta\beta^* + \gamma\gamma^*} & \frac{\tau\alpha^* + \alpha\tau^*}{+i(\gamma\beta^* - \beta\gamma^*)} & \frac{\tau\beta^* + \beta\tau^*}{+i(\alpha\gamma^* - \gamma\alpha^*)} & \frac{\tau\gamma^* + \gamma\tau^*}{+i(\beta\alpha^* - \alpha\beta^*)} \\ \frac{\tau\alpha^* + \alpha\tau^*}{-i(\gamma\beta^* - \beta\gamma^*)} & \frac{\tau\tau^* + \alpha\alpha^*}{-\beta\beta^* - \gamma\gamma^*} & \frac{\alpha\beta^* + \beta\alpha^*}{+i(\tau\gamma^* - \gamma\tau^*)} & \frac{\alpha\gamma^* + \gamma\alpha^*}{+i(\beta\tau^* - \tau\beta^*)} \\ \frac{\tau\beta^* + \beta\tau^*}{-i(\alpha\gamma^* - \gamma\alpha^*)} & \frac{\alpha\beta^* + \beta\alpha^*}{-i(\tau\gamma^* - \gamma\tau^*)} & \frac{\tau\tau^* - \alpha\alpha^*}{+\beta\beta^* - \gamma\gamma^*} & \frac{\beta\gamma^* + \gamma\beta^*}{+i(\tau\alpha^* - \alpha\tau^*)} \\ \frac{\tau\gamma^* + \gamma\tau^*}{-i(\beta\alpha^* - \alpha\beta^*)} & \frac{\alpha\gamma^* + \gamma\alpha^*}{-i(\beta\tau^* - \tau\beta^*)} & \frac{\beta\gamma^* + \gamma\beta^*}{-i(\tau\alpha^* - \alpha\tau^*)} & \frac{\tau\tau^* - \alpha\alpha^*}{-\beta\beta^* + \gamma\gamma^*} \end{pmatrix}. \quad (4)$$

From Eq.(4) , by direct calculation, it can be shown that $tr(\mathbf{M}\mathbf{M}^T) = 4M_{00}^2$.

2.2 States representing totally polarized light

Vector state $|s\rangle$ is the usual Stokes vector with four real parameters, s_0, s_1, s_2 and s_3 :

$$|s\rangle = \begin{pmatrix} s_0 \\ s_1 \\ s_2 \\ s_3 \end{pmatrix} \quad (5)$$

If $s_0^2 = s_1^2 + s_2^2 + s_3^2$, $|s\rangle$ represents totally polarized light.

Real Stokes parameters of totally polarized light can also be arranged in a complex matrix state, \mathbf{S} , as follows:

$$\mathbf{S} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} s_0 & s_1 & s_2 & s_3 \\ s_1 & s_0 & -is_3 & is_2 \\ s_2 & is_3 & s_0 & -is_1 \\ s_3 & -is_2 & is_1 & s_0 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (6)$$

3 Transformation of polarization state of light by the state representing the optical system

Mueller matrices transform four dimensional real Stokes vectors $|s\rangle$ into four dimensional real Stokes vectors $|s'\rangle$:

$$|s'\rangle = \mathbf{M}|s\rangle, \quad (7)$$

where $|s'\rangle = (s'_0, s'_1, s'_2, s'_3)^T$, s'_i are real numbers). If the Mueller matrix is nondepolarizing (optical system is deterministic) and if $|s\rangle$ represents totally polarized light then $|s'\rangle$ is also totally polarized, i.e., $(s'_0)^2 = (s'_1)^2 + (s'_2)^2 + (s'_3)^2$.

On the other hand, \mathbf{Z} matrices transform four dimensional real Stokes vectors of totally polarized light, $|s\rangle$, into four dimensional complex vectors, $|\tilde{s}\rangle$:

$$|\tilde{s}\rangle = \mathbf{Z}|s\rangle, \quad (8)$$

where $|\tilde{s}\rangle = (\tilde{s}_0, \tilde{s}_1, \tilde{s}_2, \tilde{s}_3)^T$ and $\tilde{s}_0, \tilde{s}_1, \tilde{s}_2$ and \tilde{s}_3 are, in general, complex numbers.

\mathbf{Z} matrix also transforms \mathbf{S} matrix into a $\tilde{\mathbf{S}}$ matrix:

$$\tilde{\mathbf{S}} = \mathbf{Z}\mathbf{S} \quad (9)$$

where $\tilde{\mathbf{S}}$ can be written as,

$$\tilde{\mathbf{S}} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} \tilde{s}_0 & \tilde{s}_1 & \tilde{s}_2 & \tilde{s}_3 \\ \tilde{s}_1 & \tilde{s}_0 & -i\tilde{s}_3 & i\tilde{s}_2 \\ \tilde{s}_2 & i\tilde{s}_3 & \tilde{s}_0 & -i\tilde{s}_1 \\ \tilde{s}_3 & -i\tilde{s}_2 & i\tilde{s}_1 & \tilde{s}_0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (10)$$

Note that there is a connection between $\tilde{\mathbf{S}}$ matrix and $|\tilde{s}\rangle$ vector: First column of $\tilde{\mathbf{S}}$ matrix is proportional to $|\tilde{s}\rangle$ vector, because, Eq.(8) is closely related with Eq.(9) and with their quaternion counterparts.

It can be shown that, just like complex Jones matrices, \mathbf{Z} matrices and hence $|\tilde{s}\rangle$ vectors bear total phases introduced by the optical systems for totally polarized light [4]:

$$\langle E|E'\rangle = \langle E|\mathbf{J}|E\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}\langle s|\mathbf{Z}|s\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}\langle s|\tilde{s}\rangle. \quad (11)$$

where \mathbf{J} is the Jones matrix, $|E\rangle$ is the Jones vector and $|E'\rangle = \mathbf{J}|E\rangle$.

4 Matrices defined by outer products of vector states

A complex-Hermitian matrix \mathfrak{H} is defined as an outer product of $|h\rangle$ vectors:

$$\mathfrak{H} = |h\rangle\langle h|, \quad (12)$$

where $rank(\mathfrak{H}) = 1$ and $|h\rangle$ is the eigenvector of \mathfrak{H} corresponding to the single nonzero eigenvalue.

A real matrix \mathbf{Q} is defined as an outer product of $|s\rangle$ vectors:

$$\mathbf{Q} = |s\rangle\langle s|. \quad (13)$$

A real matrix \mathbf{K} is defined as an outer product of $|s'\rangle$ and $|s\rangle$ vectors:

$$\mathbf{K} = |s'\rangle\langle s|, \quad (14)$$

or,

$$\mathbf{K} = \mathbf{M}\mathbf{Q}. \quad (15)$$

If $|s\rangle$ and $|s'\rangle$ represent totally polarized light, then it can be shown that

$$\text{tr}(\mathbf{K}\mathbf{K}^T) = 4K_{00}^2. \quad (16)$$

A complex-Hermitian matrix \mathfrak{S} is defined as an outer product of $|\tilde{s}\rangle$ vectors:

$$\mathfrak{S} = |\tilde{s}\rangle\langle\tilde{s}|. \quad (17)$$

5 The transformation

Let \mathbf{G} be any 4×4 real matrix. \mathbf{G} can be transformed into an associated complex-Hermitian matrix \mathfrak{S} by the transformation Σ [2]:

$$\mathfrak{S} = \Sigma(\mathbf{G}) = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i,j=0}^3 G_{ij} \Sigma_{ij}, \quad (18)$$

where G_{ij} ($i, j = 0, 1, 2, 3$) are the elements of the real matrix \mathbf{G} , and $\Sigma_{ij} = \mathbf{U}(\sigma_i \otimes \sigma_j^*)\mathbf{U}^{-1}$ with,

$$\mathbf{U} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & -1 \\ 0 & 1 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & i & -i & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{U}^{-1} = \mathbf{U}^\dagger = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & -i \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & i \\ 1 & -1 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (19)$$

The superscript \dagger indicates the complex conjugate and transpose, the superscript $*$ indicates complex conjugate, \otimes is the Kronecker product and σ_i are the Pauli matrices with the 2×2 identity in the following order:

$$\sigma_0 = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \sigma_1 = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \sigma_2 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \sigma_3 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & -i \\ i & 0 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (20)$$

Explicit form of the \mathfrak{S} matrix can be obtained from the following transformation table:

$$\mathfrak{S} = \frac{1}{2} \left(\begin{array}{c|c|c|c} G_{00} + G_{11} & G_{01} + G_{10} & G_{02} + G_{20} & G_{03} + G_{30} \\ G_{22} + G_{33} & -i(G_{23} - G_{32}) & +i(G_{13} - G_{31}) & -i(G_{12} - G_{21}) \\ \hline G_{01} + G_{10} & G_{00} + G_{11} & G_{12} + G_{21} & G_{13} + G_{31} \\ +i(G_{23} - G_{32}) & -G_{22} - G_{33} & +i(G_{03} - G_{30}) & -i(G_{02} - G_{20}) \\ \hline G_{02} + G_{20} & G_{12} + G_{21} & G_{00} - G_{11} & G_{23} + G_{32} \\ -i(G_{13} - G_{31}) & -i(G_{03} - G_{30}) & +G_{22} - G_{33} & +i(G_{01} - G_{10}) \\ \hline G_{03} + G_{30} & G_{13} + G_{31} & G_{23} + G_{32} & G_{00} - G_{11} \\ +i(G_{12} - G_{21}) & +i(G_{02} - G_{20}) & -i(G_{01} - G_{10}) & -G_{22} + G_{33} \end{array} \right) \quad (21)$$

It is worth noting that rank of the Hermitian matrix \mathfrak{G} can take any value between 1 – 4, in general.

Eq. (18) can be inverted by the same transformation, Σ :

$$\mathbf{G} = \Sigma(\mathfrak{G}) = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i,j=0}^3 \mathfrak{G}_{ij} \Sigma_{ij}, \quad (22)$$

6 The theorem

Let $|g\rangle$ be a vector:

$$|g\rangle = \begin{pmatrix} g_0 \\ g_1 \\ g_2 \\ g_3 \end{pmatrix}, \quad (23)$$

where g_i can be real or complex numbers.

Let \mathfrak{G} be a $rank = 1$ matrix which is defined as follows:

$$\mathfrak{G} = |g\rangle\langle g|. \quad (24)$$

Let \mathbf{Y} be a matrix associated with the $|g\rangle$ vector:

$$\mathbf{Y} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} g_0 & g_1 & g_2 & g_3 \\ g_1 & g_0 & -ig_3 & ig_2 \\ g_2 & ig_3 & g_0 & -ig_1 \\ g_3 & -ig_2 & ig_1 & g_0 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (25)$$

Theorem states that

$$\mathbf{Y}\mathbf{Y}^* = \mathbf{Y}^*\mathbf{Y} = \Sigma(\mathfrak{G}). \quad (26)$$

Theorem can be proved by showing that each element of $\mathbf{Y}\mathbf{Y}^*$ matrix is equal to the corresponding element of the $\Sigma(\mathfrak{G})$ matrix:

$$(\mathbf{Y}\mathbf{Y}^*)_{i,j} = (\Sigma(\mathfrak{G}))_{i,j}. \quad (27)$$

7 Matrices related by transformation Σ

According to the theorem it is possible to write,

$$\mathbf{Z}\mathbf{Z}^* = \mathbf{Z}^*\mathbf{Z} = \Sigma(\mathfrak{H}). \quad (28)$$

By definition, $\mathbf{Z}\mathbf{Z}^* = \mathbf{M}$, therefore, $\mathbf{M} = \Sigma(\mathfrak{H})$. In other words, Mueller-Jones matrix, \mathbf{M} , can be written as:

$$\mathbf{M} = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i,j=0}^3 \mathfrak{H}_{ij} \Sigma_{ij} \quad (29)$$

Accordingly, \mathfrak{H} matrix can be written as $\mathfrak{H} = \mathbb{Z}(\mathbf{M})$, or explicitly:

$$\mathfrak{H} = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i,j=0}^3 M_{ij} \Sigma_{ij} \quad (30)$$

Similar algebra is possible for matrices associated with polarization states of light. According to the theorem it is possible to write,

$$\tilde{\mathfrak{S}}\tilde{\mathfrak{S}}^* = \tilde{\mathfrak{S}}^*\tilde{\mathfrak{S}} = \mathbb{Z}(\mathfrak{G}). \quad (31)$$

By definition, $\tilde{\mathfrak{S}}\tilde{\mathfrak{S}}^* = \mathbf{K}$, therefore, $\mathbf{K} = \mathbb{Z}(\mathfrak{G})$. In other words, \mathbf{K} matrix can be written as:

$$\mathbf{K} = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i,j=0}^3 \mathfrak{G}_{ij} \Sigma_{ij} \quad (32)$$

Accordingly, \mathfrak{G} matrix can be written as $\mathfrak{G} = \mathbb{Z}(\mathbf{K})$ [5], or explicitly:

$$\mathfrak{G} = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i,j=0}^3 K_{ij} \Sigma_{ij} \quad (33)$$

8 An example

Let $\tau = 1$, $\alpha = i$, $\beta = 2$, $\gamma = 0$.

$$|h\rangle = \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ i \\ 2 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \mathfrak{H} = |h\rangle\langle h| = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & -i & 2 & 0 \\ i & 1 & 2i & 0 \\ 2 & -2i & 4 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad (34)$$

$$\mathbb{Z}(\mathfrak{H}) = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i,j=0}^3 \mathfrak{H}_{ij} \Sigma_{ij} = \begin{pmatrix} 3 & 0 & 2 & 2 \\ 0 & -1 & 0 & 0 \\ 2 & 0 & 2 & 1 \\ -2 & 0 & -1 & -2 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (35)$$

$$\mathbf{Z} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & i & 2 & 0 \\ i & 1 & 0 & 2i \\ 2 & 0 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & -2i & -1 & 1 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{Z}\mathbf{Z}^* = \begin{pmatrix} 3 & 0 & 2 & 2 \\ 0 & -1 & 0 & 0 \\ 2 & 0 & 2 & 1 \\ -2 & 0 & -1 & -2 \end{pmatrix} \quad (36)$$

$$\mathbf{Z}\mathbf{Z}^* = \mathbb{Z}(\mathfrak{H}) = \mathbf{M} \quad (37)$$

Let $|s\rangle$ be the state of a totally polarized light with $s_0 = 5$, $s_1 = 4$, $s_2 = 0$ and $s_3 = 3$

$$|s\rangle = \begin{pmatrix} 5 \\ 4 \\ 0 \\ 3 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{M}|s\rangle = |s'\rangle = \begin{pmatrix} 21 \\ -4 \\ 13 \\ -16 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{Z}|s\rangle = |\tilde{s}\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} 5 + 4i \\ 4 + 11i \\ 13 \\ 3 - 8i \end{pmatrix}, \quad (38)$$

$$\mathfrak{G} = |\tilde{s}\rangle\langle\tilde{s}| = \frac{1}{2} \begin{pmatrix} 41 & 64 - 39i & 65 + 52i & -17 + 52i \\ 64 + 39i & 137 & 52 + 143i & -76 + 65i \\ 65 - 52i & 52 - 143i & 169 & 39 + 104i \\ -17 - 52i & -76 - 65i & 39 - 104i & 73 \end{pmatrix}, \quad (39)$$

$$\Sigma(\mathfrak{G}) = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i,j=0}^3 \mathfrak{G}_{ij} \Sigma_{ij} = \begin{pmatrix} 105 & 84 & 0 & 63 \\ -20 & -16 & 0 & -12 \\ 65 & 52 & 0 & 39 \\ -80 & -64 & 0 & -48 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (40)$$

$$\mathbf{ZS} = \tilde{\mathbf{S}} = \frac{1}{2} \begin{pmatrix} 5 + 4i & 4 + 11i & 13 & 3 - 8i \\ 4 + 11i & 5 + 4i & -8 - 3i & 13i \\ 13 & 8 + 3i & 5 + 4i & 11 - 4i \\ 3 - 8i & -13i & -11 + 4i & 5 + 4i \end{pmatrix}, \quad \tilde{\mathbf{S}}^* = \frac{1}{2} \begin{pmatrix} 5 - 4i & 4 - 11i & 13 & 3 + 8i \\ 4 - 11i & 5 - 4i & -8 + 3i & -13i \\ 13 & 8 - 3i & 5 - 4i & 11 + 4i \\ 3 + 8i & 13i & -11 - 4i & 5 - 4i \end{pmatrix}, \quad (41)$$

$$\tilde{\mathbf{S}}\tilde{\mathbf{S}}^* = \begin{pmatrix} 105 & 84 & 0 & 63 \\ -20 & -16 & 0 & -12 \\ 65 & 52 & 0 & 39 \\ -80 & -64 & 0 & -48 \end{pmatrix}, \quad (42)$$

$$\tilde{\mathbf{S}}\tilde{\mathbf{S}}^* = \Sigma(\mathfrak{G}) = \mathbf{K}. \quad (43)$$

9 Conclusion

2×2 complex Jones matrices of deterministic optical systems act on totally polarized light states represented by two dimensional complex Jones vectors and they can keep track of the phase introduced by optical systems. On the other hand, 4×4 real Mueller-Jones matrices of deterministic optical systems act on real Stokes vectors, hence, they cannot account for the phase. But, Stokes-Mueller formalism has an advantage over the Jones formalism that it works with real-measurable states, therefore it is desirable to merge these two approaches into a single formalism that links real-measurable states with complex states.

In previous works a complex valued four parameter formulation was introduced as an extension of the real valued Stokes-Mueller formulation of deterministic optical systems, and it was shown that 4×4 complex matrices that can keep track of the phase by transforming real Stokes vectors into four dimensional complex vectors.

Recently a theorem was introduced. The theorem states that, for deterministic optical systems, there exists a relation between the outer products of real-measurable input-output Stokes vectors and four dimensional complex vectors representing the polarization state of totally polarized light.

In this note these results are combined in a compact mathematical framework which is based on four dimensional complex vectors and 4×4 complex matrices representing deterministic optical systems and polarization states of totally polarized light. Complex states

are devised to keep track of the phase. It is shown that there are relations between complex states and real states, and complex formulations meet real formulations at two points. Mueller-Jones matrix is one interface and it can be defined in terms of the complex states in two ways. Similarly, another real matrix, \mathbf{K} , which is equal to the outer product of real input and real output Stokes vectors is defined, and it is shown that complex formulations of states of light meet real \mathbf{K} matrix in two ways.

In the present framework only four dimensional vector and matrix states are discussed. Correspondence with quaternion states and Jones formalism is not included. Extensions to depolarization can be easily incorporated into the formalism as described in [2]. There may be another extension towards the Mueller quaternion also [9].

References

- [1] PhD Thesis by Russell Chipman (University of Arizona, 1987)
- [2] E. Kuntman, M. Ali Kuntman, and O. Arteaga, "Vector and matrix states for Mueller matrices of nondepolarizing optical media," *J. Opt. Soc. Am. A* 34, 80 (2017).
- [3] E. Kuntman, M. A. Kuntman, J. Sancho-Parramon, and O. Arteaga, Formalism of optical coherence and polarization based on material media states, *Phys. Rev. A* 95, 063819 (2017). 11.
- [4] E. Kuntman, M. A. Kuntman, A. Canillas, O. Arteaga, "Quaternion algebra for Stokes-Mueller formalism," *J. Opt. Soc. Am. A* 36, 492-497 (2019).
- [5] M. A. Kuntman, E. Kuntman, "A theorem on the outer product of input and output Stokes vectors for deterministic optical systems," DOI 10.5281/zenodo.32426984.
- [6] R. A. Chipman, *Handbook of Optics*, Vol. 2, 2nd ed. (McGraw-Hill Professional, 1994), Chap. 22. 7.
- [7] M. A. Kuntman, "Obtainment of Jones matrix from Mueller-Jones matrix," DOI 10.5281/zenodo.3238729.
- [8] M.A.Kuntman, E. Kuntman, "Obtainment of a Mueller-Jones matrix from two polarimetric measurements under certain symmetry conditions," DOI 10.5281/zenodo.3247006
- [9] M.A. Kuntman, A. Kuntman, "Mueller quaternion with matrix coefficients for depolarizing and nondepolarizing media," DOI 10.20944/preprints201905.0282v1